

Exploring data sharing practices through Dryad: A researcher's insight

"Data sharing becomes extremely important for **multi-institution collaborations**, as well as **training activities** we have with scholars from other laboratories who spend time here — especially international trainees". — Troy D. Wood

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Title: Chemical informatics combined with Kendrick mass analysis to enhance annotation and identify pathways in soybean metabolomics

Dataset: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.np5hq046>

Supplemental information: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14536111>

Related publication: <https://doi.org/10.3390/metabo15020073>

Funding: National Institutes of Health: S10-RR029517, NCCR; United Soybean Board; New York Corn & Soybean Growers Association

The screenshot shows the Dryad dataset administrator interface. At the top, it says "This is the administrator view of this dataset, including any unpublished, submitted changes." The dataset title is "Chemical informatics combined with Kendrick mass analysis to enhance annotation and identify pathways in soybean metabolomics". Below the title, it lists authors: Wood, Troy; Tiede, Erin; Izydorczak, Alexandra; Zemaitis, Kevin; Ye, Heng; Nguyen, Henry. It also shows the publication date: "Published Jan 28, 2025 on Dryad." The "Data files" section lists three files: "Jan 28, 2025 version files" (495.64 MB), "README.md" (3.76 KB), and "Soybean_Metabolomics_RAW_Data.zip" (495.64 MB). The "Abstract" section contains a detailed summary of the research, mentioning the use of Kendrick mass analysis and metabolomics to identify pathways in soybean metabolomics. The "Citation" section shows 4 views, 6 downloads, and 1 citation. The "Subject keywords" include "Drought, Electrospray ionization mass spectrometry, Metabolomics, Agricultural sciences, chemical informatics, FT-ICR, Kendrick mass defect, Soybean". The "Funding" section lists the National Institutes of Health (S10-RR029517, NCCR) and the United Soybean Board (1820-347 172-0130). The "Related works" section includes a primary article from "Metabolites" and supplemental information from Zenodo.

Dataset overview and analytical application

This dataset is valuable to researchers exploring the **metabolomics** and **metabolic pathways** of soybean plants, particularly those designing or analyzing plant phenotypes for adaptation to environmental stressors.

Additionally, the dataset serves as a useful reference for practitioners of mass spectrometry. It provides a practical example of applying the **Kendrick Mass Defect (KMD) principle** to complex biological specimens

— highlighting its utility in metabolomic studies and distinguishing it from more traditional applications in petroleomics.

Keywords: Kendrick mass defect; metabolomics; soybean; electrospray ionization; drought; FT-ICR; chemical informatics

Evolving practices in data sharing

Data sharing has seen significant evolution in the last decade according to Dr. Wood. In the past, metabolomics researchers would share mass spectrometry data only upon receiving a written request. Today, researchers can openly share data, including large data, using public repositories.

This shift has had a meaningful impact on the field. One of the most significant outcomes is the ability to mine publicly available datasets to identify common metabolites, which can help validate findings or refine hypotheses about biological pathways and metabolics. Dr. Wood noted that this change “should accelerate all kinds of discovery aspects in metabolomics.”

Choosing a data repository

Dr. Wood chose to explore a generalist repository for this dataset because the project involved collaborators from another institution. Additionally, the journal required the data to be publicly available in an open-access format. He mentioned, “Given these factors, and my previous positive experience, Dryad was the clear choice.”

Why Dryad?

According to Dr. Wood, one of Dryad's most valuable features is its experienced curation team—real people who provide hands-on support for every dataset to ensure quality, consistency, and usability. For this dataset specifically, a Dryad data curator identified a missing data folder (“a great quality control step”) and also offered an “excellent suggestion” to expand the user instructions to improve accessibility which is especially important for those unfamiliar with the specific instrument data formats used.

These suggestions were incorporated into the final submission and ultimately enhanced the dataset's clarity and usability for the broader research community, said Wood.

Enabling discovery through data sharing

Dr. Wood emphasized that open data sharing has transformed the landscape of plant metabolomics. Platforms like Dryad, coupled with field-wide standards and community-driven best practices, are accelerating discovery and making collaboration across labs and borders far more effective. Dr. Wood explained that data sharing “has simplified working with researchers from other institutions, especially trainees from overseas who spend weeks or months in the lab acquiring data locally, but will need access to the data subsequent to their return to their home institutions. I can see us using this more extensively in the near-term.”

By sharing this dataset, Dr. Wood hopes to support ongoing work in plant stress biology and metabolomics, while encouraging others in the field to adopt open data practices for the benefit of the wider scientific community.

Dr. Wood's tips for researchers considering open data sharing:

- **Use open formats** to ensure accessibility across platforms and collaborators.
- **Select repositories** that offer robust curation and dedicated submission support.
- **Plan for long-term access**, especially for international or temporary collaborators.
- **Provide clear usage instructions** to help users navigate data formats and avoid common accessibility issues.